

*An approach for
optimizing resource
allocation and usage
in cloud computing
systems by predicting
traffic flow*

ARTICLE HISTORY

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Fig. 3. The simple principle of the Monte Carlo simulation [9]

In order to predict the outcome of a Monte Carlo simulation, the following steps are proposed Fig 3:

Process 1: The first process is to generate a regression parametric.

Technique, $p=f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_r)$.

Process 2: Set up input generator, $x_{(c1)}, x_{(c2)}, \dots, x_{cq}$

Process 3: Model evaluation and data storage as y_c

Process 4: Process 2 and 3 must be repeated $i=1$ to n

Process 5: Calculate confidence intervals, complete statistics, and histograms based on the results.

B. Machine Learning/Data Mining

In machine learning, data are used to create mathematical models that predict or decide without explicit programming. The algorithms use "training data" to make predictions. Extreme gradient boosting regression (XGBoost), in time series forecasting, models like Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) can provide reasonable forecasts without tweaking hyper parameters [9]. This is a machine learning algorithm that uses gradient boosting to solve a variety of problems in machine learning.

Fig. 4. The simple principle of the XGBoost [11]

It is shown in Fig 4 that XGBoost is an the algorithm moves through iterations, it learns from the residuals of its neighbors. Rather than accepting the majority of the prediction results in Random Forest, it produces a more accurate prediction in this algorithm [1].

$$\hat{y}_l = \sum_{k=1}^n f_k(x_i), \quad f_k \in F, \quad (1)$$

Where f_k In regression trees, the space of trees is defined as,

f_k Assumes the form of a tree, so $f_k(x_i)$ is the outcome of tree k , and \hat{y}_l Evaluate predicted by i request (x_i) ,

C. Statistical Analysis

The Autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) is an advanced analytics technique that uses historical data and statistical models to predict future outcomes. Serial correlation is used to forecast or predict future outcomes with autoregressive integrated moving averages (ARIMA) [4]. In equation 2, the process of calculating autoregressive integrated moving averages (ARIMA) is illustrated by explaining past observations and random errors.

$$K_t = \theta_0 + \varphi_1 k_{t-1} + \varphi_2 y_{t-2} \dots + \varphi_c y_{t-c} + \rho_t + \theta_1 \rho_{t-1} + \theta_2 \rho_{t-2} \dots + \theta_h \rho_{t-h} \quad (2)$$

k_t and ρ_t in Equation. (2) this is a representation of the real value and the error at a particular time interval t , respectively, and $\varphi_i (i = 1, 2 \dots p)$ and $\theta_i (i = 1, 2 \dots h)$ During auto regression, time series is a linear regression of the p previous values accompanied by the error. Moving average $MA(q)$ describes the current rate of a time series in terms of an error at time t , and q earlier errors.

IV. DATASET

As cloud computing grows, its traffic flow increases every day. As well as uncoordinated traffic signal control and a lack of real-time data, the constant availability of the system is a critical element that cannot be ignored. Nowadays, traffic congestion has a huge impact.

In this study, data were obtained from a South African, Sandton, and automotive industry company with an IT department. As the company outsources other IT infrastructure companies, we are dealing with Cloud computing systems within the organization that are experiencing resource allocation problems. This study

collected comprehensive data from January 1, 2017, to December 31, 2022 (representing daily page loads, unique visitors, new visitors, and returning visitors).

V. SIMULATED SCENARIOS

As illustrated in Fig 5, a three-stage research design is proposed in this study as well as three predictive methods.

Fig. 5. Proposed technique

The simulation was performed using the Time Series Lab and Crystal Ball.

A model receives data and predicts it, then the model is evaluated and the results are presented in Fig 5.

Method 1 Data > Prediction Techniques > Probabilistic Models > Monte Carlo Techniques > Evaluations > Results.

Method 2 Data > Prediction Techniques > Machine Learning > XGBoost Techniques > Evaluations > Results.

Method 3 Data > Prediction Techniques > Statistical Analysis Techniques > Arima > Evaluations > Results.

VI. RESULTS

A. Evaluation Measures

In evaluation measures, errors between expected and real qualities are defined numerically [15]. The difference between them indicates how well a model did. The data set presented to the network was used to evaluate the performance of the matched network. Mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) was applied to Monte Carlo, ARIMA, and XGBoost techniques in this regard. These measures are defined by equations.

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{|S_i - V_i|}{V_i} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

Where S_i Value predicted for observation i , V_i The actual observation value i , and N Number of observations.

These prediction analysis techniques have been used to improve cloud network traffic flow predictions. Time Series Lab, Crystal Ball, and real data were used to simulate traffic flow and determine the effectiveness of the proposed model.

B. Monte Carlo technique results

Fig. 6. The normal distribution of the observed data was calculated every 20 seconds according to a 2.2 minute interval.

Fig. 7. Observed value

In Fig. 7, when traffic volume was low, the model accuracy increased; however, when traffic volume increased, the model accuracy also decreased, and the prediction was 84%, Fig 7 illustrates Monte Carlo results for the observed data. The normal distribution for the observed data was calculated every 20 seconds according to a 2.2 minute interval as explained in Fig 8. The MAPE prediction errors is 4.49 %.

C. Autoregressive Integrated Moving Averages (ARIMA)

As shown in Fig 8, the results of the Autoregressive Integrated Moving Averages (ARIMA) model were produced within 0.40 seconds, which was 0.40 seconds longer than the previous model. The MAPE prediction error is 5.59 %.

Fig. 8. Autoregressive Integrated Moving Averages (ARIMA)

In Fig. 8, when traffic volume increased, the model accuracy increased; however, when traffic volume decreased, the model accuracy also decreased, and the prediction was 79,8%.

D. Extreme Gradient Boosting Regression (XGBoost)

As shown in Fig 9, extreme gradient boosting (XGBoost) reduced training time to 10 seconds, however, prediction accuracy decreased with a minimum in error evaluation of MAPE 5.88

Fig. 9. The XGBoost prediction.

In Fig. 9, when traffic volume increased, the model accuracy increased; however, when traffic volume decreased, the model accuracy also decreased, and the prediction was 71,5%.

VII. DISCUSSION

TABLE I. COMPARISON OF PREDICTION TECHNIQUE ERRORS

Comparison of Techniques Errors			
Evaluation Items	Monte Carlo techniques	ARIMA	XGBoost
MAPE	4.49	4.59	5.88
Training time	~120 obs/sec	~0.40 obs/sec	10.43 obs/sec

In order to identify the best performing techniques, prediction analysis techniques, Monte Carlo techniques, ARIMA techniques, and XGBoost techniques were applied to a real dataset from an online cloud networking application system experiencing traffic congestion.

From 2017 to 2022, a comprehensive set of data was collected on , unique visitors, first-time visitors, and returning visitors on a daily basis.In Table 2, the Monte Carlo training method showed better performance than the ARIMA and XGBoost techniques. It improves prediction accuracy with the minimum amount of errors. Hence, Monte Carlo techniques should be incorporated into traffic prediction models or architectures

VIII.CONCLUSION

The quality of service can only be improved if future workloads are accurately forecasted and resources allocated optimally. By using this predictive analysis, cloud providers can prevent a wide range of losses, such as service outages, excessive or inadequate provisioning of cloud resources, and customer losses.

This paper compares three predictive data analytics techniques to determine how well a cloud computing system predicts future traffic parameters based on their data analytics. A bibliometric analysis review is also conducted to analyses the focus area of the proposed technique, and the findings will contribute to the design of a predictive model for managing cloud computing resources. As a result of traffic control systems' ability to predict future values of traffic parameters, their performance can be improved.

Based on bibliometric analysis, it has been found that the proposed methods are relevant for predicting cloud computing traffic flow, and Monte Carlo techniques are more efficient, than Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) and Autoregressive integrated moving averages (ARIMA) for analyzing data at a yearly level. Using hourly, daily, weekly, and monthly traffic predictions, future work will determine the most efficient time to allocate cloud computing resources. In addition, other predictive techniques will be included in order to determine which ones will be the most effective in determining the best real-time resource management in cloud computing systems.

A Monte Carlo prediction of 84% outperformed ARIMA's prediction of 79.8% and XGBoost's prediction of 71.5%, indicating that Monte Carlo is more accurate than other models when predicting traffic flow in organizational cloud computing systems. A machine learning model will be used for future studies, along with hourly monitoring and resource allocation.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

No conflict of interest has been declared by any of the authors.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Ph.D. students developed original drafts after consulting with their supervisors. They conceptualized the methodology, collected the data, prepared the experimental platform, and conducted Time Series Lab and Crystal Ball simulations.

Following the presentation, supervisors gave significant inputs to the draft, which changed the methodology and provided directions toward developing a traffic analysis model for optimizing resource allocation and utilization in cloud computing systems.

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REFERENCES

[1] Zheng, M., Huang, R., Wang, X., Li, X. Do firms adopting cloud computing technology exhibit higher future performance? A textual analysis approach. Journal of International Review of Financial Analysis, 90, (2023) . [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.irfa.2023.102866>.

[2] Apat, H. K., Nayak, R., Sahoo, B. A comprehensive review on Internet of Things application placement in Fog computing environment. Journal of Internet of Things, 23,(2023).[Online]. Available:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iot.2023.100866>.

[3] Cheng, M., Qu, Y., Jiang, C., Zhao, C. Is cloud computing the digital solution to the future of banking? Journal of Financial stability,63,(2022).[Online]. Available:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfs.2022.101073>.

[4] Luo, J., Gong, Y. Air pollutant prediction based on ARIMA-WOA-LSTM model. journal of Atmospheric Pollution Research,14,(2023). [Online]. Available:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apr.2023.101761>.

[5] Jing, J., Magnin, I.E., Frindel, C. Monte Carlo simulation of water diffusion through cardiac tissue models. journal of Medical Engineering and Physics.120,(2023).[Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.medengphy.2023.104013>

[6] Alés, A., Lanzini, F. Modelling of chemical and magnetic order in Ni-Mn-Al shape memory alloys using Monte Carlo simulations. Journal of Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials, 285,(2023). [Online]. Available:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmmm.2023.171110>

[7] Meerasri , J., Sothornvit, R. Artificial neural networks (ANNs) and multiple linear regression (MLR) for prediction of moisture content for coated pineapple cubes. Journal of Case Studies in Thermal Engineering,33,(2022). [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csite.2022.101942>

[8] Deng, T., Wu, J. Efficient graph neural architecture search using Monte Carlo Tree search and prediction network. Journal of Expert Systems With Applications,213, (2023). [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2022.118916>

[9] Lee, K., Im, S., Lee, B. Prediction of renewable energy hosting capacity using multiple linear regression in KEPCO system. Journal of Energy Reports,9 , pp.: 343-347 (2023). [Online]. Available:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2023.09.121>.

[10] Afrasiabian, B., Eftekhari, M. Prediction of mode I fracture toughness of rock using linear multiple regression and gene expression programming. Journal of Rock Mechanics and Geotechnical Engineering, 14 , pp.: 1421-1432 (2023). [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrmge.2022.03.008>.

[11] Silagyi, D.V, Liu, D. Prediction of severity of aviation landing accidents using support vector machine models. Journal of Accident Analysis and Prevention,187, (2023) [Online]. Available:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2023.107043>.

[12] Sharma, R., Awasthi, A. An embedded element based 2D finite element model for the strength prediction of mineralized collagen fibril using Monte-Carlo type of simulations. Journal of Biomechanics,108,(2020)[Online]. Available:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiomech.2020.109867>.

[13] Nadjafi, M., Gholami,P. Probability fatigue life prediction of pin-loaded laminated composites by continuum damage mechanics-based Monte Carlo simulation. Journal of Composites Communications, 32,(2022). [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coco.2022.101161>

[14] He, H., Fan, Y. A novel hybrid ensemble model based on tree-based method and deep learning method for default prediction. journal of Expert Systems With Applications, 176,(2021) .[Online]. Available :<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2021.114899>

[15] Santhusitha, D., Karunasingha, K.: Root mean square error or mean absolute error? Use their ratio as well: Information Sciences, 585, pp.: 609-629 (2022). [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2021.11.036>.

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